

Learning Preferences among Grade 10 Students in St. Paul University Surigao: Basis for Learning Framework Design

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Abstract - Saint Paul University Surigao has the main goal of providing a good quality of education. An education in which both school and students can benefit from it by upgrading teachers' quality of teaching, designing curriculum, and the level of students' skills to meet the global competencies. In this Covid-19 Pandemic, the education system has faced a great challenge which affects the learning styles of students. Knowing 'why' an activity matters because it is the first step in any individual's self-reflective process, their metacognition, and the development of their personal epistemologies (Atkinson, 2018). This study aims to develop a learning framework that can be used considering the learning preferences of incoming grade 11 students to help in creating activities that will suit their learning style. The study used the 16 Multiple Choice item VARK Questionnaire Version 8.01 ©2019 to identify students' learning styles. This researcher used purposive random sampling in grade 10 students. The results of the study find that students have unimodal learning and most of them prefer to learn aurally as their highest learning styles in the learning classroom engagement.

Keywords: Learning Preferences, VARK, Learning Framework

Introduction

Each learner has different learning preferences and styles that benefit them. Some may find they even have a dominant learning style. Others say that they prefer different learning styles in different circumstances. There is no right or wrong answer to which learning style is best for the learners— or mix of learning styles (Becton, 2022). Thus, it is important to help learners find which learning styles suit them well. According to Fleming & Baume (2006) VARK above all is designed to be a starting place for a conversation among teachers and learners about learning. It can also be a catalyst for staff development- thinking about strategies for teaching different groups can lead to more, and appropriate, variety of learning and teaching. This type of learning style helps the learners understand who they are and how to learn. In this way they can discover their own learning styles.

Different learners have different learning styles. There are lots of learning preferences to help learners and it is useful in understanding their learning ways. According to Atkinson P.S.

(2016), he believes that the best way of ensuring that students and faculty can both engage in a meaningful, positive, and fruitful learning collaboration is by designing courses well. Thus, knowing one's learning preferences is important for the growth of the learner and it is also the responsibility of the teachers to help learners find what is their preferences by using the Learning Framework Design. However, courses must also be culturally and socially aware. Students need to know why they are being asked to perform learning tasks and we should always have an answer. Knowing 'why' an activity matters because it is the first step in any individual's self-reflective process, their metacognition, and the development of their personal epistemologies (Atkinson, 2018). Therefore, this study will be a great help for the next researchers and readers to find and understand which learning preferences suit the learners.

With the current Covid-19 Pandemic the education system has faced a great challenge which affects the learning styles of students. According to Sawangsawang (2020) about this pandemic, the students have had a lack of access to technology. In teaching classes, teachers cannot control the content online, and the students cannot manage their learning, especially for practical lessons. Online learning allows students to go to all web sites that they want to know. Thus, they tend to get lost in the middle of much information. Hence, it became a struggle for some educators how to help the learners with the learning because of distractions. Moreover, teachers must be artistic in diversifying education techniques in the classroom framework by addressing students' learning needs. Learners tend to not care especially if it does not meet their learning styles. They tend to easily give up on learning. Thus, teachers entering a classroom with a weapon. It usually means that teachers must need a plan and implement what they want to do in their classroom. In planning a lesson, teachers must consider the different learning ways of students. This study explores the learning styles of Grade 10 students at St. Paul University Surigao. Finding out their Learning Preferences.

Framework

Teachers are currently expected to use student data to construct a learning plan for a varied group of learners. They must use assessments to individualize instruction for students with a variety of learning needs (Darling-Hammond & Bransford, 2005; Ryan & Feller, 2009). It is believed that all students can meet state educational standards if they are given adequate instructional support and, if necessary, accommodations. Thus, there's a need to evaluate students' learning styles and develop instructional methods to match such preferences has gained considerable momentum in the field of education (Rogowsky, B., Calhoun, B., Tallal, P., 2015) Teachers in every grade level must know the ingredients of teaching the lesson to mix it to the students' need to produce quality learning experiences.

VARK is one way in determining learning styles of the students. This method takes into account visual (V), aural (A), reading (R), and kinesthetic (K) learning preferences. This method identifies learners' preferred forms of information intake, processing, and output. The effectiveness of this pedagogy in enhancing student satisfaction and competence in the learning process. Teachers must not see students homogeneously rather see them as every unique one with many differences, and so teach them according to their differences (Cuaresma, 2008). Thus, students can

prefer one, two, or three learning styles. That is why it is important for the teachers to integrate varied activities complement to each of these learning styles to succeed in the classroom engagement.

Visual learners (V) learn by looking at images, graphics, and films with a lot of detail. They prefer to portray printed information with symbolic tools such as arrows, flowcharts, graphs, models, and hierarchies. They demonstrate concepts to others by creating a picture or image. Teachers use overheads, the chalkboard, pictures, graphs, maps, and many other visual items to entice a visual learner into knowledge (Roelle, Kelly 2019). Some students need to *see* information to learn it, and this "seeing" takes many forms from spatial awareness, photographic memory, color/tone, brightness/contrast, and other visual information that will help their learning more meaningful.

Aural learners (A) pay close attention to what teachers say. In a study conducted by Cohen and Wolvin (2011), story-listening is argued to be very essential for auditory learners. Students prefer to listen rather than take comprehensive lecture notes; they enjoy conversations and seminars, as well as listening to speaker mp3 recordings. Aural learners can remember information by reading aloud or simply mouthing it quietly.

Read/Write learners (R) obtain information from printed texts such as lecture notes, handouts, and textbooks. They are also excellent note-takers or teachers doing dictations. According to Kazazoglu (2013), he pointed out that dictation signifies the receiving of some spoken input that will be written immediately by students after their accurate hearing. The students listen to an oral text and write down what they hear. The passage can be presented more than once, and it needs to be presented in segments, so that learner had time to process the language and before writing it down.

Kinesthetic learners (K) value hands-on learning, practical application, modeling, and real-world experience. They prefer touch, movement, and contact in their learning environment. They dislike simply listening, particularly in an image-rich atmosphere; kinesthetic learners are often passive in the classroom. Himmele (2011) states students must take activities into higher-level thinking. It is also a lot of fun when students are asked to do this in a group. And students were encouraged to participate in groups, it makes them more comfortable in conducting activities in the classroom and outside, and using this game will facilitate them to learn voluntarily.

According to Jemi Sudhakar (2017), "The best classroom engagement comes from not having only a good lesson planning for each student but must have also a view of the big picture in their future to see how every students fit into the grand scheme of things." Learning styles will inevitably differ among students in the classroom, the teachers should try to make changes in the classroom that will be interactive to every learning style.

Framework Design

This framework will serve as a guide in making a curriculum map as we have already determined the learning preferences of the learning style of grade 10 students as they will take their journey as grade 11.

This researcher's made learning guide for teachers based on VARK results of Grade 10 students will be useful in a way that teachers will have an ease of making a learning map. And this is aligned also with the SPUS-OBE, and Most Essential Learning Competencies of Dep.Ed. Teachers may utilize the given activities to enhance the engagement in the classroom and be used in planning a learning plan or they may add other teaching activities that will suit depending on their topic.

Learning Style Framework Guide for Teachers

Method

This study utilized quantitative methods through descriptive research design. The study used the 16 Multiple Choice item VARK Questionnaire to identify students' learning styles.

The participants were the grade 10 students in this academic year 2021-2022. The researcher believes that the result of the study will be beneficial for both teachers and students for the next academic school year 2022-2023 – it can lead to enhanced student learning as they use their current understanding to discover, construct and incorporate new knowledge, understanding and skills; and it involves teachers considering range of assessment opportunities to suit the needs, interests and abilities of individual students

The research used a purposive random sampling technique to select the respondents; forty percent of the population were being selected; hence, the total number of students were 240 and the samples are 96 to utilize in this study. The samples answered the VARK Questionnaire for the students' learning styles. The result from the Questionnaire was gathered and used by the researcher to develop a learning framework design to address the learning preferences of incoming grade 11 students.

The researcher used the following statistical tool; *Frequency Count and Percentage Distribution*. This tool was used to treat the profile of the respondents.

Results and Discussion

Table 1.

Profile of the participants

Profile Variables	f (n=96)	%
Sex		
Male	55	57.29
Female	41	42.71
Age		
13-14	19	19.79
15-16	70	79.92
17-18	7	7.29

Table 1 shows that among the purposely and randomly selected 96 Grade 10 students in St. Paul University Surigao 55 (57.29%) were male and 41(42.71%) were female. This reveals that the majority of the students were male. As to their age, 19 (19.79%) were 13 to 14 years old, 70 (79.92%) were 15 to 16 years old, and 7 (7.29%) were 17 to 18 years old. This implies that the majority of the Grade 10 students were 15 to 16 years old.

Table 2

Learning Styles of the Participants

Unimodal n=72 (75.00%)		Bimodal n=18 (18.75%)		Trimodal n=6 (6.25%)		Quadrimodal
Visual	3 (3.13%)	VK	1 (1.04%)	VAR	2 (2.08%)	VARK
Aural	28 (29.17%)	AK	14 (14.58%)	VRK	2 (2.08%)	
Read/Write	14 (14.58%)	RK	3 (3.13%)	ARK	1 (1.04%)	
Kinesthetic	27 (28.13%)			VAK	1 (1.04%)	

The table shows the learning styles of the participants. As to the modalities, it is presented that a total of 72 (75.00%) students preferred a single modal learning style (unimodal), it is either visual, aural, read/write and kinesthetic, 18 (18.75%) preferred two learning styles (bimodal) and 6 (6.25%) students preferred to use three learning styles (trimodal). These students had a balanced

set of preferences, which means students prefer information to arrive in a variety of modes in learning. However, no student-participant preferred quadrimodal.

Out of the 72 students who preferred unimodal, 28 (29.17%) are aural (A) learners, students who pay close attention to what teachers say ; 27 (28.13%) preferred kinesthetic (K) style, learners who prefer touch, movement, and contact in their learning environment; 14 (14.58%) preferred read/write (R) style, learners who obtain information from printed texts such as lecture notes, handouts, and textbooks; and 3 (3.13%) preferred visual learning style, these learners who learn by looking at images, graphics, and films with a lot of detail.

Eighteen (18) students chose two modes of presentations where 14 (14.58%) preferred aural and kinesthetic (AK) style, 3 (3.13%) preferred read/write and kinesthetic (RK) style, and 1 (1.04%) preferred visual and kinesthetic (VK) style.

Six students preferred three modes of presentation where 2 (2.08%) preferred visual, aural, and read/write (VAR) and visual, read/write, and kinesthetic (VRK) styles and 1 (1.04%) preferred aural, read/write and kinesthetic (ARK) and visual, aural, and kinesthetic (VAK) styles.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, it was concluded that, the dominant learning preference among Grade 10 students at St. Paul University Surigao was Auditory, followed by Kinesthetic, and then Reading/Writing and combination of Auditory and Kinesthetic. Moreover, the least preferred learning styles are the combination of Visual and Kinesthetic; combination of Auditory, Reading/Writing, and Kinesthetic; and combination of Visual, Auditory and Kinesthetic. Most students can learn effectively as long as the instructor provides different learning activities in the areas assessed in VARK. Active learning might be enhanced in classrooms by lectures, group discussions, debates, speeches, role playing, dancing, hands-on activities, experiments, answering worksheets, presentations, story reading, critique paper, and many more.

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